

TEACHER TRAINING IN THE EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF GIFTED CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role and importance of teachers' professional preparation in the upbringing and development of gifted children. The psychological and pedagogical characteristics of gifted learners are analyzed, and the key theoretical, methodological, and practical competencies required for effective work with gifted children are identified.

Keywords: gifted children, teacher training, pedagogical competence, individual approach, educational process.

At the present stage of social development, the upbringing of intellectually capable, creative and independent-thinking individuals is one of the priority tasks of the state educational policy. In particular, the issue of identifying, supporting and developing gifted children is one of the urgent problems facing the education system. In this process, the professional training of the teacher is of decisive importance. Working with gifted children requires the teacher not only in-depth knowledge of the subject, but also psychological, pedagogical and methodological competencies. Therefore,

this article analyzes the level of training of teachers in the upbringing and development of gifted children, its content and significance from a scientific and theoretical perspective.

One of the important tasks facing the education system today is the identification of gifted children, their comprehensive support and development. The development of society, the development of science and technology, and the growing need for intellectually capable personnel are further increasing the relevance of this issue. In this process, the professional training of the teacher is a decisive factor. Gifted children are students who have high abilities and intellectual potential in a certain type of activity, are prone to creative thinking, independent decision-making, and solving complex problems. They usually have such characteristics as fast learning, high cognitive activity, rich imagination, and strong interest. At the same time, working with such children requires a special pedagogical and psychological approach from the teacher. In the effective upbringing and development of gifted children, the teacher participates not only as an educator, but also as a guide, advisor, and motivator. The teacher must timely identify the child's abilities and organize the educational process taking into account his individual capabilities. This requires a high level of professional training from the teacher.

The teacher's preparation for working with gifted children consists of several main components. First of all, theoretical preparation is of great importance. The teacher must have sufficient knowledge about the psychology of giftedness, age characteristics, and the laws of personal development. This knowledge helps to correctly assess and develop the child's internal capabilities. Secondly, methodological preparation determines the teacher's professional skills. Traditional

teaching methods may not be effective enough when working with gifted children. Therefore, the teacher must be able to effectively use innovative educational technologies, problem-based teaching, methods based on project and research activities. These methods serve to develop children's creative and independent thinking. Thirdly, psychological preparation also plays an important role. Gifted children are often emotionally sensitive, they may have difficulties in communicating with peers or a decrease in interest in the learning process. The teacher must be able to correctly understand such situations, support the child, and exert pedagogical influence aimed at increasing his motivation. Practical training also ensures the teacher's success in working with gifted children. By organizing various science clubs, olympiads, competitions, and creative projects, the teacher makes a practical contribution to the development of the child's abilities. In this process, the teacher must constantly enrich his experience.

In order to improve the preparation of teachers for working with gifted children, it is important to organize special advanced training courses, seminars and trainings in educational institutions. Also, the study and implementation of advanced pedagogical practices, the establishment of a system of experience exchange serve to increase the professional potential of teachers.

In conclusion, the process of educating and developing gifted children requires a high level of theoretical, methodological, psychological and practical training of the teacher. The higher the professional skills of the teacher, the more fully the potential of gifted children will be revealed. Therefore, the issue of preparing teachers for working with gifted children should be in the center of constant attention in the modern education system.

List of used literature

1. Каримова В.М. **Педагогик психология**. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2018.
2. Давлетшин М.Г. **Ёш ва педагогик психология**. – Тошкент, 2017.
3. Богоявленская Д.Б. **Психология одаренности**. – Москва, 2002.
4. Рензулли Ж. **Развитие одарённости у детей**. – Москва, 2005.
5. Хасанбоев Ж. **Замонавий педагогика назарияси**. – Тошкент, 2019.
6. Қодиров Б.Р. **Иқтидорли болалар психологияси**. – Тошкент, 2016.
7. Слостёнин В.А. **Педагогика**. – Москва, 2014.
8. Абдуллаева Ш.А. **Инновацион таълим технологиялари**. – Тошкент, 2020.